

Get to know Your Environment: Medicinal California Native Plants

By

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A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements to Graduate with University

Honors

The University Honors Program

California State University Fullerton

May 2022

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Date:

12 May 2022

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Scientific name: *Heteromeles arbutifolia*

Common Name: Christmas Berry, California Holly, Toyon

Family: Rosaceae

Biom: Chaparral, Coastal scrub, Oak woodland

Uses: California Holly flowers during the summer, and begins developing fruit in the autumn which persists through winter. This fruiting season has meant that historically, the berries of *Heteromeles arbutifolia* have been used as a food source during winter, when other food sources are not available. These berries taste like a powdery tart apple, and can be eaten raw, but are much better cooked. Historically the main medicinal use for *H. arbutifolia* is to treat women's conditions, such as irregular menses. This treatment was prepared by mashing up the flowers of toyon and steeping the resulting mush in hot water. The leaves of this plant were also steeped into a tea to treat similar conditions. The Chumash people also used a leaf based tea as a blood purifier (emetic).

The Chumash people used Toyon berries to treat ailments such as senile dementia. They also made tea from the bark and leaves of the Toyon bush to treat aches and pains. Pultuses from the leaves have also been used to soothe sores.

Active Ingredients:

Lupeol, icaraside, acetate, betulin, and flavonoids.

(known to be anti inflammatory. Also possibly protect from the build up of amyloid toxicity in the brain.)

Fun fact:

The California Holly plant is where the city "Hollywood" gets its name.

Scientific name: *Sambucus nigra*

Common Name: Blue Elderberry, Black Elder, Elderberry

Family: *Adoxaceae*

Biom: Coastal scrub, Oak woodland

Uses: The elderberry flowers from spring through summer, and develops fruit in the late summer. The flowers of the elderberry plant can be steeped into a tea that nearly all Californian Native Americans used to treat colds, flus and fevers and premenstrual syndrome and menstrual pain. Elderberry flowers can also be used to make a plethora of culinary items such as mead, syrup, soda, kombucha, jam and much more! The fresh berries of this plant can cause nausea in some, however when dried, the berries have a very sweet flavor pleasant to the palette. These berries can also be used as a laxative and are an excellent source of vitamin C. The flowers of the elderberry can also be made into a shampoo by crushing them between hands with some water. This was particularly meaningful to Native Americans to help control lice.

Active Ingredients: Rutin, ebulin, lectins, triterpenoids, sterols, glycosides, tannins.

Sambucol (*Sambucus nigra* abstract) is actually available to be purchased commercially in the US and has performed well in clinical trials, showing to both reduce flu duration by 3-4 days as well as increase immune response against viral infections, including HIV.

Scientific name: *Rhus integrifolia*

Common Name: Lemonade Berry

Family: Anacardiaceae

Biom: Coastal Scrub

Uses: The berries of *Rhus integrifolia* are very tasty, and can be eaten or sucked on to alleviate thirst. This fruit can also be ground and mixed with water to create a drink that tastes very similar to lemonade. It is theorized that Native Americans also used this species to alleviate colds and lung congestion, by brewing the leaves of *R. integrifolia* into a tea.

Active Ingredients: *R. integrifolia* contains moronic acid, betulonic acid, robusta flavone and morello flavone which are known to be antiviral compounds. Hinokiflavone is another compound found in *Rhus integrifolia*, which is possibly an anticancer compound. *R. integrifolia* also contains compounds associated with antibacterial and anti inflammatory effects.

Lemonade Berry Recipe:

After harvesting lemonade berries, place into a glass (not plastic) container without washing them. Then cover the berries with water and let soak for 2-12 hours depending on the desired flavor, stirring occasionally. Drain the mixture through a fine meshed sieve to separate the berries from the liquid and you have lemonade berry juice! This juice can be used for “lemonade” by adding sugar and water to taste, or made into syrup, jelly or even candy!

Scientific name: *Quercus lobata*

Common Name: Valley Oak

Family: *Fagaceae*

Biom: Oak woodland, Savanna

Uses: The valley oak tree flowers in March and April (though the blooms are not conspicuous.) *Q. lobata* has been used historically as a vital food source during more barren winters. The acorns produced by *Q. lobata* could be gathered and stored for later consumption, though they are susceptible to weevils and mold. These acorns could be made into soup or baked into bread by many native americans, some even would eat them as a porridge. Sometimes a thin acorn soup was used by the Chumash tribe to treat diarrhea and other fairly commonplace ailments. In the past some Native Americans also used an infusion of powdered oak bark to treat arthritis, skin problems and burns.

Active Ingredients:

Acorns of *Q. lobata* are about 6% protein, 30% carbohydrates and 66% fat, this is great nutritional value especially for a resource so readily available in nature. Acorns shouldn't be eaten raw.

Scientific name: *Salvia apiana*

Common Name: White Sage

Family: *Lamiaceae*

Biom: Coastal scrub, Chaparral

Uses: White sage puts out flowers from August all the way to October, and fruits will mature from September to October. The leaves of white sage have a plethora of uses, one of the most vital historical uses was as shampoo for the Luiseno and Cahuilla tribes, who were, within the missions, not allowed to bathe everyday. This helped control lice in particular. The leaves of white sage were also used as a deodorant to mask the smell of human body odor, especially while hunting. A drink made by steeping *S. apiana* leaves in cold water was used to treat sore throat, colds and flus. The leaves have also been used to treat toothache, stomach ache, asthma and even to cleans wounds. The seeds and stems of the young plants can be used as a food source. The leaves of sage are to this day burned by some to drive away harmful spirits or invite friendly ones.

Active Ingredients of note: *Salvia apiana* contains cineole eucalyptol which can help soothe a sore throat. It also contains monoterpenoids which can be used for pain or even anxiety relief.

Scientific name: *Romneya coulteri*

Common Name: Matilija Poppy, Fried egg poppy

Family: *Papaveraceae*

Biom: Chaparral, Coastal Scrub

Uses: The matilija poppy flowers from March to July and has the largest flower of any plant native to California. *Romneya coulteri* was used by the chumash indians for skin conditions and irritations. To treat skin irritations the leaves and flowers of the matilija poppy can be crushed into a poultice and applied to the irritated portions of skin for relief. The leaves, young stems and some parts of the flower were also steeped into a tea. This tea was used to alleviate symptoms of food poisoning, such as cramps and stomach pain. This infusion also functions as a mild sedative. *Romneya coulteri* has also been used as a source of hydration, since the stalks of the plant contain a drinkable watery substance.